

A Study on Issues, Challenges and Ways to Overcome in Promotional Analysis of a Brand

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.122

Citation:

Sivaraja, G
Charmila, K. “A
Study on Issues,
Challenges and Ways
to Overcome in
Promotional
Analysis of a Brand.”
*Shanlax
International Journal
of Management*,
vol. 6, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 152–54.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567717>

Mr. G. Sivaraja, B.E, MBA, PGCBA.,

Assistant Professor, Vijay Institute of Management

Ms. K. Charmila, B.E, MBA.,

Assistant Professor, Vijay Institute of Management

Abstract

Marketing is a golden treasure where promotion is the way to go. Marketer should be proactive than being reactive since we are living in a competitive world. This paper explains how a brand marketer can approach customers based on segmentation. Figuring out the previous mistakes of the self and from mistakes of other players will avoid future discrepancies in the product promotion. So this paper motivates everyone and suggests on handling the issues with the examples listed inside the paper. They will find it useful for their future presentation, if so.

Keywords: Promotion, Pre promotion, Strategies, Overcoming challenges.

Introduction

Brand is a familiar word used by many people globally. It also plays a vital role in marketing aspect. Promotion is the key associated with the brand which delivers the ideas to consumers and also captures the emotions and identifies the purchasing ability towards the brand.

Promotion creates an awareness of a brand and paves a way for maintaining a good relationship with the consumer.

Every company does an analysis of the promotion which is post promotion works. It's usually reactive in nature. What if they do analysis even before promotion? We are in the updated technological world which looks for a better feed. It remains always hungry, so a marketer should know proactive techniques to promote the brand. It's always a well known fact that prevention is better than cure.

Promotion

The key 'Promotion' is mainly used to attract more number of customers and through old customer relationship inviting new customers. We have come across few mentioned below

1. Quantity

- 1) Free! Buy one get one
- 2) Innovative cross-selling and up-selling
- 3) Free samples

- 4) Particular day offer
- 5) Personalized promotions targeting particular customer segment

2. Price discount

- 1) Particular % off per item
- 2) Flat rate per item
- 3) Discount vouchers

3. Coupons

- 1) On-line
- 2) Email
- 3) Mobile

4. Shipping promotions

- 1) Free delivery of product
- 2) Money off on delivery item by means of a selected ship mode
- 3) Cash on Delivery

Some of the promotions may motivate the customers to purchase a product. In spite of such attractive offers, a customer may not take advantage of every offer that comes their way.

Promotion Strategies

The below keys will definitely promote the brand

1. Perfect media (TV, Blogs, Social Media, FM, etc)
2. Right time
3. Good content – Message
4. Promising
5. Pre Promotion plans
6. Updates
7. Positioning

Promising

A Promise is a mantra which needs to be positioned in consumers mind till their life time.

For example, Bata looked for everyone to wear their shoes but during mid 80's due to competition there was a change in price. After that scenario BATA products seems costly for 'C' class family. Prices are not affordable, so those people started thinking that BATA is looking only for 'A' class family customers. That resulted in losing 'C' class family customers.

A Promise should be a Promise forever!

Pre-promotion plans

1. A Brand marketer should realize the importance of place and culture before marketing. For example, A Muslim community says Eating 'Pork' is Haram (against their religion). And Eating 'Beef' is against Hindu religion. So, incorporating steps unknowingly will lead to religious fight and demolition of brand.

2. Customer behavior changes from A to Z or vice versa. So try to find out customer behavior and what they are looking for. Find out those and promoting the brand will lead the sales into rapid growth.

For example, Diapers and Nutritious cereals food are much required for babies. But that differs from Milk. Milk is much required to all the age group.

Updates

One should always keep an eye on update. No update in the product, no gain in the market.

Competitor’s secret weapon is the update option. They will defeat their opponent in a short span of time like a flash.

For example, Guerrilla marketing by Docomo smashing the sales of Airtel like Tele Networks. Now Jio is into the same action.

Docomo introduced pulse scheme (paisa/second). Jio introduced free sim for all and net offer (1gb/day).

Positioning

The word ‘Positioning’ means how our products are registered in consumers mind. Positioning should be a long lasting concept.

For example, Singapore zoo ‘River Safari’ painted their vehicles innovatively and attracted huge number of customers. Perth Zoo buses quoted ‘Come to the zoo before the zoo comes to you’. These bus wraps looks terrific and funny as well. Sometimes, Pictures without wordings may convey the meaning and capture a place in peoples mind.

Overcoming Challenges

Challenges remains challenges until we think of a solution or remedy. Unsorted Challenges creates a bad image for the brand. Thereby we lose customers, sales and profit. Let us see how we can overcome via known proverbs.

1. Look before you leap – Look at your new competitors. Never imagine their strength or underestimate the size.
2. Even Elephant do slips – Never underestimate you, compared to giant competitors.
3. Stitch in time saves nine – Act immediately whenever if promotion goes in the wrong direction or when you find the promotion is leading customers/consumers in a wrong way
4. Stand on your own leg – Develop own apps (let it be user-friendly) and update regularly. Answer the customers on regular basis. Sort out their problems.

Conclusion

To become a brand is not an easy task. It needs a lot of input, groundwork, etc. A close watch on the trends within the industry and also the overall global scenario should be done in order to enter the market and for the existing ones to survive. There is always one way to survive in the current scenario – “its simple – Be Creative”.

References

1. <https://www.mumbrella.asia/2014/01/singapore-zoo-gets-creative-home-promote-river-safari-attraction>
2. <https://www.kaocollins.com/inktank/16-innovative-bus-wrap-designs/>
3. https://www.business-standard.com/article/management/40-years-ago-and-now-how-bata-put-its-foot-down-114112601251_1.html